

Powering Ships, Cutting Carbon: The FuelSOME Approach to Multifuel SOFCs

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Abstract. The maritime sector faces an accelerated decarbonization trajectory driven by the International Maritime Organization's 2023 greenhouse-gas (GHG) strategy [1] and the European Union's FuelEU Maritime regulation [2]. Against this regulatory backdrop, the FuelSOME project develops and validates a multifuel solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) system tailored to ocean-going vessels [3]. The system targets efficient operation on ammonia, methanol and hydrogen—preferably sourced from renewable energy or waste streams [4]—supported by a fuel supply and quality framework and by techno-economic and life-cycle sustainability assessments (LCSA) [5]. This paper outlines the project rationale, system concept and interim progress, while situating FuelSOME in the scientific and industrial state of the art. Key activities include (i) screening fuel pathways and defining SOFC-grade fuel quality requirements, (ii) advancing stack-level tolerance and degradation management under multifuel operation [6], (iii) designing a flexible 6 kW SOFC architecture with harmonized balance-of-plant for multiple fuels [7], and (iv) implementing an integrated TEA/LCSA to compare against conventional marine propulsion [8]. Initial results indicate successful design and manufacturing of stack modules suitable for multifuel operation, component validation under varying atmospheres, and development of reforming/cracking units for ammonia and methanol [9]. Socio-environmental and economic assessments are progressing, with no major risks identified to date. The near-term objective is the laboratory validation of a 6 kW system with $\geq 50\%$ electrical efficiency and ≥ 500 h operation under marine-relevant profiles. Collectively, these outcomes point to the technical feasibility and sustainability potential of multifuel SOFC systems as a pathway to deep decarbonization in deep-sea shipping [10]

Keywords: solid oxide fuel cell, maritime decarbonization, Hydrogen, Ammonia

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